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Rolling-out pioneering carbon dioxide capture and transport chains from inland European industrial facilities: A techno-economic, environmental, and regulatory evaluation

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ABSTRACT

Large-scale deployment of CO₂ capture, transport, and storage (CCTS) requires the rolling-out of extensive value chains. This study presents the development, design, techno-economic, environmental, and regulatory analysis of four pioneering chains that capture and condition CO₂ from existing European industrial plants and their multi-modal transport to selected ports in Northern Europe. The pioneering chains can avoid between 65% and 87% of the industrial emissions, including scope 3, with a cost of CO₂ avoided ranging between 100 and 300 €/tCO₂. The economic and environmental performance of the CCTS chains are substantially affected by the geographic location of the industrial emitters and the CO₂ volumes to be transported. The analysis relies on the assumption that the four industrial plants would be early movers. While, in the future, technology maturation and infrastructure development are expected to reduce costs and emissions associated with the CCTS chain, this study quantifies and presents the current economic burden that must be overcome to initiate a needed widespread implementation of CCTS.

1. Introduction

The imperative to address climate change and the rising levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere has become increasingly urgent. Carbon dioxide capture, transport, and storage (CCTS) has been identified as a critical component of climate strategies to mitigate emissions [1]. CCTS offers a promising avenue for capturing CO₂ emissions from large point-source emitters, including from hard-to-abate industrial sectors, preventing them from entering the atmosphere, and storing them safely and permanently underground. However, deploying CCTS is a complex endeavour, with multifaceted technical, economic, environmental, and regulatory challenges that require careful analysis.

In Europe, emitters, particularly those situated in central regions, will face the hurdle of having to transport large amounts of CO₂ (on average 250 ktCO₂/y per emitting plant [2]) most likely to port within the continent for subsequent storage offshore, which is being more extensively developed compared to onshore storage. Pipelines have been identified as the most cost-effective CO₂ onshore transport mode for volumes larger than 2 MtCO₂/y regardless of the transport distance [3].

It is, thus, evident that a cross-border pipeline network will be essential for the transport of substantial CO₂ volumes required to meet European countries' climate objectives. This assertion is supported by a wealth of literature. [4–15].

Studies that considered point-to-point connections or simple networks showed that under certain conditions (such as CO₂ reservoirs with low injection pressure, long distances) liquid CO₂ transport has an initial economic advantage with respect to CO₂ transport by pipelines [7]. However, such an advantage disappears with increased volumes of CO₂ to be moved [4] and when operational feasibility aspects are considered [16]. The trend is confirmed and reinforced when looking at the design of more extensive networks, which are dominated by CO₂ transport by pipelines [9]. An analysis for emitters in Switzerland from the WtE sector has investigated the cost-optimal infrastructure rollout, including several options for CO₂ transport [13]. The results are again heavily relying on pipelines, while only ship and barge transport are competitive alternatives but, evidently, limited by the proximity

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Table 1
Main characteristics of the four pioneering chains considered in this study.

	Cement plant Heidelberg materials	Cement plant Heidelberg materials	Waste-to-energy plant KVA Linth	Pulp mill Stora Enso
Location	Hannover (DE)	Góraźdże (PL)	Niederurnen (CH)	Skutskär (SE)
Total CO ₂ emissions [MtCO ₂ /y]	0.69	1.77	0.16	1.10
Biogenic share of CO ₂ emission [MtCO ₂ /y]	0.04	0.19	0.08	1.10
CO ₂ conc. in flue gas [%]	15%	18%	12%	12%
Distance from harbour [km]	235	450	997	0

of navigable waters. In a following study [14], backup transport solutions such as trucks are indicated as an important complement to the pipeline-network on the ground of increased resilience. Although different transport modes are included in certain studies [5], the consensus around the cost-effectiveness of pipelines led many studies to focus solely on them, e.g., to develop supply chains in the UK [6], in the Netherlands [8], in Germany [10], in Northeast China [11] as well as for the entire Europe [12] or China [17].

However, the long planning and constructing phases for a large infrastructure, e.g., pan-European, pose a significant challenge – particularly considering that planning has only recently started – and will require cross-border cooperation. Moreover, this construction will likely be a phased process (for instance a three-stage pipeline development path is proposed by Huang et al. [18]), with initial implementation centred around major industrial clusters near CO₂ storage facilities and northern ports. The first pipeline segments might not extend so far to reach larger emission sources located inland, eager to implement CCTS as early movers. Some of these pioneers are already investigating solutions for CO₂ capture and transport that can be implemented in the near term. Near-term implementation will require mature technologies and existing infrastructure [19]. Although the range of CO₂ capture and transport technologies commercially available today is limited, there exist off-the-shelf solutions that can be deployed [20].

Overall, the literature review shows that several studies have investigated the optimal design of CCTS supply chains: yet the studies mainly focus on long-term optimal solutions [21], while overlooking the set of challenges and opportunities that early movers are expected to face. Nonetheless, shedding some light on such an issue is extremely important given the urgency to kick-start the deployment of CCTS and the strong ambition shown by some industrial actors to take the lead. This contribution tackles this multifaceted problem with a holistic approach that considers all relevant aspects: technological, economic, environmental and regulatory. A similar comprehensive approach has hardly been applied in the literature and is missing for the pioneering type of implementations considered here. In line with the presented overarching goal, this contribution focuses on the design of CCTS value chains relying on commercially available CO₂ capture and transport technologies to enable potential implementation within the next two to three years. Four large-scale emitters are considered, willing and interested in becoming early CCTS movers, situated in diverse European locations, and belonging to hard-to-abate sectors, i.e., waste treatment, pulp-and-paper production, and cement manufacturing [22]. For each emitter, a specific CCTS chain is designed to capture and transport CO₂ from the source to a delivery harbour, from which the CO₂ will be collected by a storage operator. The chains are analysed based on their techno-economic and environmental performance. The ultimate objective is to outline a comprehensive set of recommendations for deploying CCTS by early movers, with a specific focus on advantages, disadvantages, and strategies for easing the burden encountered by these pioneers.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the four emitters considered in this analysis, and Section 3 presents the methodology adopted. Results are presented in Section 4, and Section 5 presents the lessons learned and general recommendations that can be extrapolated from this work. Section 6 concludes the paper by highlighting the contributions and potential impact of the work.

2. Pioneering chains

In this study, four pioneering chains are developed, designed, and evaluated. The chains are termed “pioneering” as they consider the selected CO₂ emitters as early movers and the CCTS chains as first-of-their-kind. The CO₂ point-source emitters correspond to four existing industrial plants currently advocating the deployment of CCTS as an urgently needed tool to curb their emissions:

- a cement plant from Heidelberg Materials (HM) in Hannover, Germany,
- a cement plant from Heidelberg Materials (HM) in Góraźdże, Poland,
- a waste-to-energy (WtE) plant from KVA Linth, in Niederurnen, Switzerland,
- a pulp mill from Stora Enso (SE) in Skutskär, Sweden.

These emitters cover a wide spectrum of relevant conditions for deploying CCTS at an industrial scale: (i) they exhibit different flue gas characteristics in terms of volume and composition; (ii) they present case-specific challenges that are representative of several industrial applications, e.g., availability of surplus energy; (iii) finally, their geographical locations introduce sets of different challenges for transporting the captured CO₂ to the selected delivery harbour. All in all, these four plants offer a comprehensive picture to understand what it takes for the near-term roll-out of CCTS chains from industrial emitters in Europe. In addition, the different degrees of utilization of bio-resources (leading to different shares of biogenic CO₂ emissions) by the four industries allow for investigating opportunities to deliver carbon dioxide removal (CDR). Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the four pioneering chains considered in this study, while Fig. 1 illustrates their geographic location, closest harbours, and the potential CO₂ storage site. In the following, these four chains are referred to simply using their location.

There are several planned and emerging permanent CO₂ transport and storage hubs in Northern Europe [23–29]. Among them, the Northern Lights site in Norway and the Porthos site in the Netherlands are currently the only commercial storage projects under construction with significant capacity and clear expansion plans [24,26]. In light of the several hubs being developed in Northern Europe, in this study the pioneering chains are designed to capture, condition, and transport CO₂ to a selected port in Northern Europe using different modes. From the port, it is assumed that CO₂ is transported directly via ship to one of the hubs being developed, although cost and emissions related to this final step are not accounted for in this study. It is essential to be aware of such boundaries when analysing the results. For instance, whenever an emission reduction figure or a cost is reported, these refer to the amount of CO₂ avoided by capturing, conditioning, and transporting CO₂ from the industrial site to the selected port. The transport via ship to the final storage site will result in additional emissions and increased costs. Nonetheless, the decision to focus on the delivery harbour as the final point for the analysis in this study offers a strategic advantage that extends beyond the immediate context of a specific storage site: by choosing the harbour as the endpoint, it is ensured that the results obtained can be extrapolated and applied to any storage hubs accessible from the same harbours and currently under development. This choice also acknowledges the potential for collaboration with other stakeholders, such as emitters, transport operators, or storage operators, to

Fig. 1. Geographic location of the four emitters considered in the analysis, closest harbours, and commercial CO₂ transport and storage hubs in construction or at an advanced stage of development [23].

optimize transportation from harbours to storage sites by clustering emissions from various sources.

3. Methodology

For the four CCTS chains described in Section 2, CO₂ is captured using a solvent-based absorption process and then conditioned for multi-modal transport in liquid state at 15 barg, as described in Section 3.1. The CO₂ transport options considered are presented in Section 3.2. These first-of-a-kind chains are evaluated using the consistent cost assessment methodology described in Section 3.3. The methodology for accounting of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is outlined in Section 3.4.

3.1. Technology for CO₂ capture, conditioning and transport

3.1.1. CO₂ capture and conditioning

CO₂ absorption using aqueous solutions of monoethanolamine (MEA) has been commonly used as the reference technology in benchmark studies of CO₂ capture processes [30,31]. However, the solvent blend of AMP (amino-methyl-propanol) and PZ (piperazine) has recently been proposed as an alternative benchmark for CO₂ capture processes primarily due to (1) its relatively high maturity, (2) its lower specific reboiler duty for solvent regeneration, and (3) its lower thermal and oxidative degradation compared to other solvents [32]. The solvent AMP has a high absorption capacity but a low reaction rate of CO₂ absorption, which is improved by adding PZ to the AMP solution. The solvent blend of 27 wt.% AMP–13 wt.% PZ is known as the CESAR1 solvent [33], although the relative content of the two components may vary for different applications. In this study, a 33 wt.% AMP–12 wt.% PZ solvent composition is used. Such composition was selected based

on preliminary analyses where additional compositions (i.e., 27 wt.%–13 wt.%, and 20 wt.%–20 wt.%) were tested and compared in terms of energy efficiency at fixed lean loading.

A schematic of the AMP-PZ capture process is shown in Fig. 2, which is very similar to a standard MEA capture process. The flue gas (stream 1) is pre-cooled in a direct contact cooler (DCC) before entering the absorber (stream 4), where the CO₂ is absorbed. A water wash section tops the column to recover solvent from the exhaust gases. In the case of the two cement plants and the pulp-and-paper plant, a second water-wash section is needed to remain within the regulated limits of amine emission to air. While the CO₂ depleted gas (stream 5) is released to the atmosphere, the CO₂-rich solvent (stream 7) is sent to the stripper. The solvent is heated with steam in a reboiler for regeneration. The purified CO₂ leaves from the top of the stripper (stream 16), while the lean solvent (stream 10) is circulated back to the absorber. A thermal reclaimer is included to purify the solvent and allows for spent solvent disposition. A lean-rich heat exchanger is used for energy recovery. The capture process for the cases considered here has been simulated using Aspen Plus V10. A rate-based modelling approach is used, relying on the unsymmetric electrolyte NRTL property method (ENRTL-RK) [34]. The model is further tuned to represent the behaviour of the selected solvent, including properly selected interaction coefficients as well as equilibrium constants and kinetic parameters.² The model is validated against experimental data within the range of solvent operating temperatures reported by Brüder et al. [35] (the experimental data reported in Fig. 4 from the referenced paper were considered).

Steam is normally used for regenerating the CO₂-rich solvent. The following options for using biofuels for steam production have been

² Specific information on the modelling parameters can be made available upon request by contacting the corresponding authors

Fig. 2. Process flowsheet of the reference CO₂ capture unit.
Source: Adapted from [31].

considered: (1) biogas for cement and WtE plants, and (2) biomass for the pulp mill. Those solutions were selected to minimize the additional CO₂ emissions due to steam supply, although their cost is expected to be higher than conventional options, e.g., natural gas-fired boilers. Although the direct CO₂ emissions from biogas and biomass combustion are considered to a very large extent as biogenic, the utilization of biogas and biomass is not considered free from environmental impacts. In line with the principles outlined in Section 3.4, the indirect emissions related to energy use and up- and downstream processes are included. More details on the environmental implications of utilizing different solutions for heat supply can be found in Burger et al. [36]. Additionally, the consideration of bio-resources for each location took into account the availability of the specific resource, e.g., the availability of biomass at the pulp mill. It should be remarked that the selection of bio-based solutions for the pioneering chains should not be interpreted as an indication of the feasibility of the use of bio-resources for widespread deployment.

The captured CO₂ needs to be compressed and/or liquefied to the desired conditions depending on the selected transport solution. In this study, liquefaction at a pressure of 15 barg is considered as currently only transport at this pressure is commercially available. A schematic of the CO₂ liquefaction process is shown in Fig. 3, while more information on the conditioning cycle selected can be found in Deng et al. [37]. The process has been studied using rigorous mass and energy balance models developed with Aspen HYSYS V10 for all the relevant process units using property packages and parameters reported by Deng et al. [37]. The SQP-based optimization utility within HYSYS has been used to minimize the overall specific energy consumption of the system considering the following decision variables: (1) the pressure ratios of the various compressor stages, (2) the valve outlet pressures, and (3) the cooler outlet temperatures.

3.2. CO₂ transport

As this study focuses on pioneering chains, only CO₂ transport options that can be implemented in the near term are considered, i.e., mature technologies that do not require any considerable green-field infrastructure outside of the emitter's site or the receiving harbour. This implies that several solutions are outside the scope of this study,

e.g., large intermediate storage facilities and filling stations at exchange sites, the construction of new railway stations, the construction or refurbishment of pipelines, and technologies under development, such as dedicated barges and ships.

All transport options considered in this study carry CO₂ in the liquid state at medium pressure (15 barg and -27 °Celsius at loading). Two possible approaches are included. First, CO₂ can be loaded into ISO tank containers (typically referred to as isotainers), each holding approximately 20 t CO₂. These isotainers have the same dimensions as typical freight containers and can be loaded onto trucks, trains, barges (on rivers), and ships (on open waters). The CO₂ remains in the container throughout the whole supply chain, and the isotainers are exchanged between transport modes by means of a crane. Second, CO₂ transport relying on fixed tanks installed on dedicated trucks and trains, which generally have a larger capacity than isotainers. More details about the different transport options can be found in Oeuvray et al. [3].

The topology and existing infrastructure at each emitter site are decisive concerning the potential deployment of specific transport solutions. The cement plant in Hannover has a private railway station and can accommodate transport by truck. However, despite being connected to the Stichkanal Misburg, a branch of the Mittellandkanal, there is currently no cargo barge operation from there, and dedicated barge transport is not considered in this study. The situation is similar for the cement plant in Górażdże, which has a private railway station too, but no water connection because the nearby Oder river is not navigable for large vessels. The WtE plant KVA Linth is far from any navigable river, and railway transport is not a viable option (the plant has no private railway station, while the closest freight railway stations do not permit transshipping of CO₂). There is, nonetheless, road access, and the plant is located close to the highway allowing for truck transport. The pulp mill in Skutskär is situated directly by the sea and has a private harbour; therefore, there is no need for transport from the emitter to the harbour.

3.3. Methodology for cost assessment

Due to their early mover status, the four pioneering chains are assessed as first-of-their-kind. Consequently, although their cost analysis incorporates typical investment costs, fixed operating costs, and

Fig. 3. Process flowsheet of the CO₂ liquefaction unit.
Source: Adapted from [37].

variable operating costs, it is anticipated that the expenses associated with these four pioneering chains will be higher compared to their implementation at a later stage when technologies are more mature and have progressed beyond the early phases of commercialization. To account for these higher costs, this study follows the guidelines developed and described by Roussanaly et al. [38,39] for cost evaluation of low-carbon technologies. The following sections provide a summary of the assessment, while additional details can be found in Appendix C.

The cost evaluations are performed on an EBIDTA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization) basis and reported for 2019. To reflect the higher financial risk of FOAK, an economic lifetime of 20 years and a discount rate of 10% are assumed.

3.3.1. Capture and conditioning

As commonly adopted in literature, a bottom-up approach is used to evaluate the investment cost of the CO₂ capture and conditioning process, whereby the direct cost of each equipment is evaluated using Aspen Process Economic Analyzer. Subsequently, these costs are combined with a set of factors and cost elements to obtain the total capital requirement, as illustrated in Fig. 4. For example, the following aspects are considered to reflect the higher costs of first-of-a-kind applications [38,39]:

- Increased design margins and material thicknesses to reflect an oversized design and adhere to more stringent design standards;
- Redundant equipment and additional spare equipment allowance to limit the risk of failure and extensive shutdown;
- Higher process contingencies to reflect current low maturity;
- System contingencies to reflect the potential cost associated with the integration of the capture and conditioning units with the industrial plant and site;
- Higher construction period to reflect the delays often observed for projects undertaken for the first time;
- Higher discount rate to reflect the financial risks associated with such projects.

Similarly, while the estimation of the labour, maintenance, and utility costs is based on a commonly adopted approach (outlined in Appendix C), higher costs are also foreseen due to the first-of-a-kind nature of the pioneering chains. Additional labour and maintenance costs are expected in the first years of operation due to e.g., the time required for learning and training, and other inefficiencies. In addition, lower capacity factors are adopted for the first two years of operation,

Table 2

Costs of utilities used for the techno-economic analysis.

Utility	Unit	Value
Process water [42]	€/m ³	6.65
Cooling water ^a	€/m ³	0.039
AMP solvent [43]	€/2015/kg	8
PZ solvent [43]	€/2015/kg	6
Solvent sludge disposal [44]	€/2015/t	205
Molecular sieve [45]	€/t	3600
Steam from biomass ^b	€/GJ	14.1
Steam from biogas ^c	€/GJ	13.9

^a Based on discussion with industrial partners in the project.

^b Based on a biomass cost of 18 €/MWh.

^c Based on a biogas cost of 30 €/MWh.

i.e., 40% and 65%. Finally, utility consumption is assumed to be 15% higher than the basis during the first three years of operation [41]. The costs of utilities assumed are reported in Table 2. As electricity costs and carbon intensity differ significantly depending on the location, different values are adopted for each pioneering chain, see Table 3.

3.3.2. Transport

The assessment of the transport costs is based on the methodology described by Ouevray et al. [3]. The techno-economic assessment considers capital and operational expenditures derived from the transport distance and duration; they include infrastructure, rolling material, labour, maintenance, fuel, insurances and taxes, administrative fees and supplements. The data has been collected directly from industrial and logistics companies whenever possible. Based on the identified transport-exchange terminals and the feasible connections, a network outlining feasible paths leading to a specific harbour is generated for each emitter, as shown in Fig. B.14. This network can be visualized as a directed graph, whereby the nodes represent transport exchange sites where a transport mode exchange can occur, and the edges represent direct connections between two nodes. The weight of each edge is determined by the transportation cost associated with the available transport option for that connection. The Yen's algorithm [48] is used on the simple directed graph to determine the cost-effective routes from a source to a specified harbour.

3.3.3. Cost of CO₂ avoided

The economic performance of the pioneering chains is mainly assessed through the cost of CO₂ avoided (CAC), i.e., the cost to avoid

Fig. 4. Bottom-up approach for the estimation of the total capital requirement.
Source: Modified from [40].

Table 3
Electricity costs and carbon intensity for the CO₂ capture and conditioning plants.

Plant	Country	Costs	Intensity	Ref.
HM Hannover	Germany	106.5 €/MWh	521 kgCO ₂ /MWh	[46]
HM Górażdże	Poland	77.5 €/MWh	1047 kgCO ₂ /MWh	[46]
SE Skutskär	Sweden	45.5 €/MWh	46 kgCO ₂ /MWh	[46]
KVA Linth	Switzerland	75.8 CHF/MWh	50 kgCO ₂ /MWh	[47]

a unit of CO₂ emissions. The CAC is defined as the ratio between the net present value of CCS implementation cost (including capital and operational expenditures) and the discounted amount of CO₂ emissions avoided throughout the years [49]:

$$CAC = \frac{NPV_{CCS}}{\sum_i \frac{m_{CO_2,avoided,i}}{(1+r)^i}} \quad (1)$$

with NPV_{CCS} being the net present value of total annual CCS costs (which may vary from year to year), $m_{CO_2,avoided,i}$ the mass of CO₂ avoided by CCS implementation in year i over the full life cycle and r the discount rate.

3.4. Methodology for life cycle assessment

The life cycle assessment (LCA) quantifies the climate change and other environmental impacts of the four pioneering CCTS chains from the CO₂ capture up to the delivery of the CO₂ to the nearest harbour. The LCA system boundary includes all emissions of the CCTS chains while excluding the point source itself (see Fig. 5). The processes in the system boundaries are grouped into three sub-systems: Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 emissions, following the definitions of the greenhouse gas (GHG) protocol [50]. Scope 2 emissions include the whole life cycle of the electricity generation, while Scope 3 emissions include all indirect emissions from up- and downstream processes. Upstream processes can be the production of steel and concrete for construction, while downstream emissions occur, for example, in the treatment of waste streams.

The LCA is based on the work of Burger et al. [36] and follows the methodology defined in ISO 14040:2021 and ISO 14044:2021 [51,52]. The global warming impact (GWI) of the pioneering chains is assessed using the global warming potential over a 100-year time horizon from the “Environmental Footprint” version 3.0 impact assessment methods [53]. All impacts are scaled on a functional unit, which is the product or service delivered by the plant. Therefore, the functional unit is one ton of clinker ($t_{clinker}$) for both cement plants, one ton of

incinerated municipal solid waste (t_{waste}) for the WtE plant, and one air-dried ton of pulp (adt_{pulp}) for the pulp mill.

By quantifying the chain’s GHG emissions, the LCA shows the potential for (i) the amount of avoided CO₂ and (ii) the amount of CDR to be generated:

$$m_{CO_2,avoided} = m_{CO_2,em \text{ w/o CCTS}} - m_{CO_2,em \text{ w/ CCTS}} - CC_{chain} \quad (2)$$

with $m_{CO_2,avoided}$ being the avoided CO₂ emissions, CC_{chain} the climate change impact of the chain (i.e., the direct and indirect emissions caused by the implementation of the CCTS chain), $m_{CO_2,em \text{ w/o CCTS}}$ the amount of CO₂ emissions prior to implementing CCTS, and $m_{CO_2,em \text{ w/ CCTS}}$ the amount of CO₂ emissions still being released after the implementation of CCTS. The CDR potential of the CCTS chains is linked to the biogenic fraction of the plant emissions and is defined as:

$$m_{CO_2,CDR} = m_{CO_2,bio, em \text{ w/o CCTS}} - m_{CO_2,em \text{ w/ CCTS}} - CC_{chain} \quad (3)$$

where $m_{CO_2,bio, em \text{ w/o CCTS}}$ is the amount of biogenic CO₂ emissions released by the plant to the atmosphere prior to implementing CCTS.

As the system boundary ends at the nearest harbour (see Fig. 5), it excludes maritime transport to the storage site and the subsequent geological storage. Both steps cause GHG emissions that must be included to quantify the overall avoided CO₂ from the point source. Consequently, the presented LCA quantifies the potential of the CCTS chains for CO₂ avoidance and for delivering CDR, focusing on capture and inland transport, which have the largest environmental impact [36]. For example, an LCA of the maritime CO₂ transport and offshore storage at the Northern Lights storage site estimates life cycle emissions of 2.6% for the total amount of CO₂ injected [54]. The influence of these steps of the CCTS chain on the overall CO₂ avoidance potential is expected to be limited.

While the goal of CCTS chains is the reduction of global warming intensity of the industrial point source, CCTS chains unavoidably lead to other environmental impacts. Thus, fifteen additional environmental impact categories are analysed besides GWI to quantify the extent of burden-shifting. The results for all environmental impact categories are reported in Appendix A.

Fig. 5. System boundary of the LCA divided into Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3 emissions.

Fig. 6. Illustration of the pioneering chains from the four emitters to the closest harbours.

4. Results

4.1. CCTS chains designs

The transport configurations selected for the pioneering chains are shown on a map of Central/Northern Europe in Fig. 6. In detail, the

cement plant in Hannover, Germany, is connected with the harbour of Wilhelmshaven by dedicated road transport. Trucks effectuate daily roundtrips on the 235 km-long connection to transport the captured CO₂ from the cement plant to the harbour. The cement plant in Góraźdże, Poland, is connected via railway to the harbour of Szczecin, located 450 km apart. Five trains composed of dedicated wagons

Fig. 7. Breakdown of CO₂ emissions without and with CCTS: Fossil (grey) and biogenic (blue) emissions prior to the implementation of CCTS; CO₂ emissions (purple) still remaining after the implementation of CCTS i.e., due to the limited CO₂ capture rate; indirect emissions caused by CCTS divided into scope 1 (brown), 2 (red) and 3 (orange); CO₂ emissions removed (light green) thanks to the implementation of CCTS; CO₂ emissions reduced thanks to the implementation of CCTS.

Table 4
CO₂ emissions and avoidance values for the pioneering chains.

		CO ₂ emissions w/o CCTS (biogenic/fossil)	CO ₂ emissions captured	Scope 1, 2 and 3 CO ₂ emissions due to CCTS	CO ₂ avoided w/ CCTS (reduction/removal)
Hannover	$\frac{\text{kgCO}_2}{\text{t}_{\text{clinker}}}$	868 (52/816)	777	129	648 (648/0)
Góraźdźe	$\frac{\text{kgCO}_2}{\text{t}_{\text{clinker}}}$	884 (97/786)	790	221	570 (570/0)
Niederurnen	$\frac{\text{kgCO}_2}{\text{t}_{\text{waste}}}$	1241 (645/596)	1113	188	925 (596/330)
Skutskär	$\frac{\text{kgCO}_2}{\text{adt}_{\text{pulp}}}$	2041 (2041/0)	1837	57	1780 (0/1780)

convey the CO₂ daily. The total distance travelled is longer for the CO₂ captured at the WtE plant in Niederurnen, located in Switzerland, a land-locked country. In this case, the CO₂ is loaded into isotainers, which are transported first by truck to Basel and then by barge, over the 1000 km from Niederurnen to the Rotterdam harbour. Finally, due to its coastal location and infrastructure, the pulp mill in Skutskär, Sweden, has direct access to a suitable port.

4.2. CO₂ emissions accounting and avoidance potential

Fig. 7 shows the CO₂ emissions breakdown for the four pioneering chains in terms of specific CO₂ emissions, defined as the amount of direct and indirect CO₂ emissions per unit of industrial product, with and without the implementation of CCTS. Table 4 reports the related emissions and avoidance values. Without CCTS, each plant is responsible for a given amount of CO₂ emissions depending on the industrial process, divided into fossil (grey bar) and biogenic (blue bar) emissions. For example, the biogenic CO₂ fraction of the emissions from the Hannover cement plant corresponds to 6% (52 of the total 816 kgCO₂/t_{clinker}), while for the Skutskär pulp mill the fraction is 100%.

The implementation of CCTS implies that a large amount of the industrial CO₂ emissions is captured and conditioned on-site to be made ready for transport. The share of CO₂ emissions that is captured is

defined by the CO₂ capture rate (CCR). The CCR corresponds to 90% for all the capture plants, a value that is slightly reduced due to CO₂ losses in the conditioning process (the actual CCR is above 89% for all chains). Therefore, ca. 11% of the CO₂ produced by the plant is still being emitted after the implementation of CCTS (purple bar). In line with common practice in the literature, a CCR of 90% for the capture process was selected for consistent comparison among the CCTS chains, despite the fact that higher CCR are feasible and the optimal CCR is likely case specific [55]. Upon implementation of the CO₂ supply chain, direct and indirect emissions (scope 1, 2, and 3) occur and must be accounted for (stacked bars — each scope is represented with a different colour, i.e., orange, red, brown). These additional emissions reduce the potential for CO₂ avoidance (reduction and/or removal).

The amount of CO₂ avoided can be obtained as the difference between the total CO₂ emitted to the atmosphere without CCTS and the CO₂ emitted after its implementation; the latter stems either at the plant because the CO₂ capture rate is less than 100%, or directly and indirectly along the CO₂ chain. The CO₂ avoided term comprises both CO₂ emissions removed (light green bar) and CO₂ emissions reduced (dark green bar). The relative share depends on the fossil and biogenic content, respectively, of the total CO₂ emissions, in accordance with the principles outlined in Section 3.4. The CO₂ reduction expresses the decrease of net fossil CO₂ emissions released into the atmosphere

Fig. 8. Breakdown of the specific energy consumption with respect to the elements of the pioneering chains. The total specific primary energy consumption for each chain corresponds to 3473 MJ/t_{clinker} and 3477 MJ/t_{clinker} for the cement plants in Hannover and Góraźdże, respectively; 5568 MJ/t_{waste} for the WtE plant; and 7938 MJ/adt_{pulp} for the pulp mill.

with respect to the plant without CCTS. The CO₂ removal implies that there is also a net removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere due to the implementation of CCTS, meaning that the CO₂ uptake of the biogenic source is larger than the overall CO₂ emissions to atmosphere. In other words, CO₂ removal takes place when a positive difference between the amount of biogenic CO₂ emissions without CCTS on one hand, and the total CO₂ emissions with CCTS, including uncaptured as well as direct and indirect emissions due to CCTS, on the other hand, is achieved. For example, the pulp mill uses primarily bio-resources in its industrial process, while the WtE plant considered here processes a large fraction of biogenic waste. Thus, the implementation of CCTS at these two plants results in a large CO₂ removal potential, as it can be noted both in Fig. 7 and in Table 4 where the removal potential is 1780 kgCO₂/adt_{pulp} and 330 kgCO₂/t_{waste}, respectively. Conversely, the cement plants, at today's conditions, although reaching significant CO₂ reduction (between 570 and 648 kgCO₂/t_{clinker}), do not yield CO₂ removal.

Based on the emissions accounting described, the pioneering chains exhibit a potential to avoid 65% to 87% of their emissions.

A substantial contribution to the residual emissions is associated to the energy needs for implementing CCTS. The relative breakdown of the specific primary energy consumption with respect to the chain elements is presented in Fig. 8, while the absolute numbers are reported in the caption. The main energy inputs are power and heat for the capture and conditioning processes, as well as fuels (i.e., trucks and barges) or electricity (i.e., trains) for the means of transportation. The capture process is by far the main contributor to the energy consumption for all the chains, with a share of 70% to 86% of the total. Energy-wise, transport plays a significant role for the chains located far from a harbour (e.g., 18% for the Niederurnen chain).

The breakdown of the specific CO₂ emissions with respect to the chain elements is presented in Fig. 9. Although the energy requirement for capture is dominant regardless of the chain, its impact on the environmental performance is more limited. This is due to the utilization of biofuels such as biogas and biomass to produce steam for the capture process, for which the direct emissions are largely accounted for as biogenic. Conversely, despite having a smaller energy requirement, power-driven processes, such as CO₂ liquefaction, may have a significant carbon footprint depending on the carbon intensity of the electricity mix. The two cement plant chains, for instance, source electricity from national grid mixes that still rely heavily on fossil fuels.

Overall, the most impactful factors on the GHG emissions results are: (1) the types of fuels used and their associated CO₂ intensity, (2)

Fig. 9. Breakdown of the specific CO₂ emissions with respect to the elements of the pioneering chains.

the CO₂ intensity of the electricity grid mix, and (3) the length of the transport route from source to harbour, whereby the geographic location of the emitting industrial plants affects the grid mix and the transport route significantly.

4.3. Economics of the CCTS chains

The large impact of geographic location is also revealed by the analysis of the economic performance of the pioneering chains. Fig. 10 shows both the breakdown of the cost of CO₂ avoided with respect to chain elements and cost terms. The capture plant is, on average, the dominant factor, as previously noted in the literature [9]. Similarly to the energy and emissions figures, the transport cost becomes relevant in certain cases (e.g., the Niederurnen chain) depending on the location of the industrial plant. A long distance to the nearest port requires the design of a complex, extensive, and expensive transport route. Vice versa, the proximity to a port obviously allows to reduce the cost of CO₂ transport. In addition, an industrial site located in a favourable position, such as along a navigable river, leads to lower transport costs. The geographical location also affects the cost of the energy sources (primarily the cost of electricity) and their carbon footprint. An example of a pioneering chain benefiting from a favourable geographic location is the pulp mill chain. The pulp mill is located on the coast (indeed, no transport costs are included) and in a country (i.e., Sweden) characterized by relatively inexpensive and clean electricity. The WtE plant in Switzerland offers a different example: it can make use of relatively clean electricity locally, but it faces major energy and cost burdens because of the need to transport the CO₂ to the port of Rotterdam, i.e., through a fairly long transport route, along which fossil fuels play still a major role.

Other factors that significantly impact the costs are the scale and the characteristics of the industrial flue gas to treat: larger scales lead to smaller specific costs of the capture and conditioning units, at least with the technologies considered [56]. For instance, the scale contributes to a cost gap of ca. 50 €/t CO₂ for capture and conditioning between the largest industrial installation (i.e., the Góraźdże cement plant) and the smallest one (i.e., the WtE plant). Potentially, the characteristics of the flue gas can have an impact too, especially in terms of CO₂ concentration. However, the range of concentrations of the four industrial flue gases considered, i.e., between 12% and 20% in volume, yields differences in cost of capture, which are possibly below the intrinsic uncertainty in determining the costs of the entire chain [57].

Concerning the contribution of various cost terms, the OPEX is normally the major component, when all its terms are summed together. Among those, the variable OPEX related to steam production

Fig. 10. Breakdown of the cost of CO₂ avoided of the pioneering chains with respect to (1) chain elements (left bar) and (2) cost terms (right bar).

(i.e., OPEX Steam) and the variable OPEX “others” (a term that includes non-energy related costs such as the cost of chemicals and the costs incurred in operating the transport logistics) are the two largest costs, although the latter, being mainly related to transport, is more case-specific. CAPEX is consistently a substantial share (21%–33%) of the overall CAC, irrespective of the industrial case.

All the factors described combine to determine the CAC of the pioneering chains. The CAC achieved is shown in Fig. 11, including the effect of different boundaries of indirect emissions considered (i.e., scope 1, 2 and 3). The pioneering chains exhibit a CAC between 100 and 300 €/t CO₂. A direct comparison with other results from the literature would be misleading because the CCTS chains are case specific and because the present cost estimations are performed on a FOAK basis. Provided that, a qualitative comparison against similar CCTS chains stemming from WtE plants in Switzerland [13] and in Italy [21] achieved, approximately, 50% lower costs. This is in line with expectations, as further discussed in Section 5.1.

A close look to the results shows that effect of the additional emissions along the chain may be significant — e.g., the final cost figure is increased by 40% in the case of Góraźdże. The impact of designing a complex value chain can also be noted, for instance, by comparing the results for Niederurnen and Skutskär. The need for long transport routes, as is the case for industrial emitters located in inland Europe, implies significant costs for operating the transport logistics (a key factor explaining the difference between the grey bars), and direct and indirect emissions along the chain (particularly scope 1 and 2 emissions, in brown and red in the figure). Increased costs and emissions lead to higher CAC values.

5. Discussion and learnings

5.1. Cost of full-scale demo capture facilities

A distinctive aspect of the cost evaluation presented in this study for the pioneering chains is that it is performed on a FOAK basis, as explained in Section 3.3, to reflect the higher cost typically associated with such early movers. Considering the very limited number of such assessments performed in literature for CCTS value chains, it is interesting to understand how such an evaluation compares to a Nth-of-a-kind (NOAK) evaluation (as commonly performed in literature³) and the main contributions to the increase in FOAK costs with respect to NOAK. To this end, the costs of capture and conditioning for the Skutskär chain were evaluated also on a NOAK basis. The NOAK approach resulted in a cost of 71 €/t CO₂ for capture and conditioning compared to 93 €/t CO₂ for the FOAK case, which thus yields 30% higher costs, all other things being equal. Fig. 12 shows the breakdown of the capture cost using both FOAK and NOAK approaches. CAPEX is, as expected, more impacted⁴ than fixed or variable OPEX. The cost

³ This means a “what-if” type of NOAK evaluations, describing the “aspirational NOAK cost” that is obtained if cost and performance targets are successfully met. Conversely, a “what-will” type of NOAK evaluation describes the “expected NOAK cost” or “projected NOAK cost” that will likely be reached by a technology at a point in time. More insights are presented in Roussanly et al. [39].

⁴ The total capital requirement (TCR), Fixed OPEX and Variable OPEX contributions (in €/t CO₂) to CO₂ capture cost are 133, 62, and 3%, respectively, in the FOAK than the NOAK.

Fig. 11. Cost of CO₂ avoided (CAC) of the pioneering chains and effect of different boundaries of the direct and indirect emissions considered. Capture and transport cost (grey bars) does not account for the direct and indirect emissions along the chain. The effect of the direct and indirect emissions (scope 1, 2 and 3) on decreasing the CO₂ avoidance, ergo increasing the CAC, can be noted added on top (brown, red and orange bars, respectively).

Fig. 12. Comparison of FOAK vs. NOAK capture and conditioning cost for the Skutskär pioneering chain.

difference is mainly⁵ attributed to the bottom-up factors used (Table C.7 in Appendix C provides an overview of the main factors used for FOAK and NOAK evaluations). In addition, the level of equipment redundancy contributes significantly to this cost gap.

The adoption of FOAK approach provides valuable insights into the heightened costs involved in the capture and conditioning of CO₂ anticipated for early deployment. It is imperative to acknowledge that these costs are poised to decrease as additional facilities are commissioned and technological advancements occur,⁶ it is important to note that “what-if” NOAK estimates are not expected to evaluate the actual cost of a plant post-demonstration i.e. once technology is mature. For that a “what-will” type of NOAK estimates would be more appropriate. A “what-will” type of NOAK estimates must be derived from FOAK estimates through learning rates and other aspects [39]. For instance, potential sources of this cost reduction may include:

⁵ The FOAK cost methodology leads to TCR (in M€) 93% than in the NOAK, which in turn also increases fixed OPEX. However, other elements such as the shorter project duration, the discount rate, and the assumed lower efficiencies in the first couple of years also play a role in the higher cost observed in the FOAK case.

⁶ As highlighted by Roussanaly et al. [39].

- As observed for most new technologies, investment and operating costs tend to decrease with increased capacity deployment thanks to learning-by-doing and research. This is typically owed to process modifications and improvements based on practical experience, reduced need for redundancies and over-design, more reliable integration with the plant, modularization, standardization, etc. Such effects are already observed for CCS applications at coal-based power plants [58].
- The cost-effectiveness of energy supply, particularly in absorption-based CO₂ capture, hinges significantly on the steam cost for solvent regeneration (as shown in Fig. 10). In this study, steam is assumed to be generated via biogas and biomass combustion to mitigate potential challenges in heat recovery and integration with the industrial plant under consideration, and, in the WtE case, to maintain the same power output. However, such methods incur substantial costs (and greenhouse gas emissions if reliant on fossil fuels). A proven approach to alleviate these expenses involves recovering surplus heat from the industrial plant or nearby facilities to produce steam [59]. Depending on the specifics of each case, this may vary in complexity, ranging from direct steam extraction of sufficient quality to the recovery of low-quality steam necessitating further enhancement through methods like heat pumps.

5.2. Cost of transport for early movers located in inland europe

The costs of transport associated with the supply chains of the emitters considered in this study are shown in Fig. 10. The associated transport pathways can differ in cost, roundtrip duration, required logistics, and operational-to-capital expenditures ratio. Alternative networks to transport CO₂ from source to port were also assessed and resulted in cost increases of up to 20% compared to the optimal ones. This limited variability suggests the relative robustness of the CO₂ transport segment of the chain. It is worth noting that the costs of transport reflect mainly the distance, because the existing transport options are modular and thus offer limited economies of scale. As empirical guideline for inland transportation costs with pioneering options based on the chains evaluated in this work, the cost from emitter to harbour scales linearly with distance, with a unitary cost of ca. 1 €/tCO₂ transported over 10 km.

Transport technologies such as dedicated transport and pipelines are more efficient than container-based transport, although they require more infrastructure and thus a longer lead time [3]. Furthermore, they offer economies of scale. As the amounts of CO₂ transported will grow, the transport costs are expected to decrease by 50%–75% over the entire supply chain [3]. Pipeline networks are planned to connect coastal regions with industrial regions, and thus allow for an economical and continuous delivery of captured CO₂ [26,60].

5.3. Supporting the burden of early movers and valuing CDR

As highlighted in the earlier sections, the CO₂ avoidance cost from capture to the harbour of the four considered pioneering chains varies between 100 and 300 €/tCO_{2,avoided}. The costs of CO₂ transport from the harbour to the storage hub and of CO₂ storage will likely add at least several tens of €/tCO_{2,avoided}. For reference, these costs are significantly higher than the current CO₂ emissions price under the European Union’s Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), thus making CCTS deployment from the facilities under the EU ETS not economically viable today.

A significant challenge for the four CCTS chains analysed here is the higher costs incurred as early movers, which might result in the decision to delay implementation. To overcome this key challenge to implementation, several possibilities could be explored [61].

Support to partly cover the burden of the investment costs could be sought at the national or European Union level [61]. Such measures include contributions to up-front costs, grants to cover engineering studies, e.g., Front End Engineering Design (FEED), loan support (enabling preferential interest rates, access to debt capital, and loan guarantees), and tax credits. A similar strategy could be seeking national or EU-level operational subsidies to create predictable revenue streams [61]. This could be achieved through, e.g., tax credits and/or contracts-for-difference.

Another opportunity for some of these CCTS chains is to create the largest value from the generated CDR. As highlighted in Fig. 7, two of the chains considered here can generate significant levels of CDR through the capture and permanent storage of biogenic CO₂ produced by these facilities. Indeed, high-quality CDR in voluntary carbon markets or private financial agreements are valued at prices as high as 700 \$/tCO₂ [62,63]. Let us consider the case of the WtE plant located in Niederurnen, Switzerland. Without any revenue from selling the generated CDR, the plant faces a cost of CO₂ avoided for its fossil emissions of 450 €/tCO_{2,avoided}.⁷ A revenue of 400 €/t CDR would roughly half the cost of CO₂ avoided; if such revenue increased to 750 €/t CDR, the cost would be reduced by more than 90%. While this aspect could present significant opportunities for CCTS implementations that could enable CDR, it is important to note that further work and proper regulations are required to develop suitable business models and prevent double accounting.

Finally, another possibility consists in passing down the additional costs due to the implementation of CCTS to the end-users of the relevant products. Indeed, as highlighted by recent studies [64–66], a high CO₂ avoidance cost does not necessarily result in a significant cost increase for the end-users of the final products derived from these industrial plants. The end-users could easily absorb this cost increase if the proper mechanisms are in place.

5.4. International and european regulatory framework for CCTS

While CCTS has reached technical readiness for implementation, the legal and regulatory framework essential for its effective large-scale deployment and oversight still needs revision and updating.

The International and European regulatory framework is working to enable the implementation and deployment of CCTS technologies through global agreements and national legislation. International law serves as the cornerstone for CCTS activities, emphasizing the importance of responsible practices and cross-border cooperation. Key international agreements, such as the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention) and the London Protocol, are instrumental in shaping the regulatory landscape for CCTS, particularly regarding protecting the marine environment and permanent CO₂ storage beneath the seabed.

The EU regulatory framework for CCTS revolves around critical components, notably the EU ETS and the CO₂ Storage Directive. The integration of CCTS into the EU ETS is crucial, given that this legislation forms the cornerstone for reducing greenhouse gas emissions across various sectors. The CO₂ Storage Directive establishes a comprehensive regulatory framework within the EU, addressing key elements such as cross-border transport of CO₂ for storage, third-party access to CO₂ transport networks, qualitative standards for CO₂ purity, and the issue of long-term liability.

In light of these advancements, it is crucial to recognize that, despite the technical readiness of CCTS, legal questions and challenges must be effectively addressed for the large-scale and successful implementation of these technologies [67].

⁷ This value assumes that the entire economic burden for the implementation of the CCTS chain is allocated to the fossil emissions, which are roughly 65% of the total emissions.

6. Conclusions

This article presents the development, design, and techno-economic, environmental, and regulatory analysis of four pioneering CCTS chains with the goal of providing a clear picture of the challenges and opportunities of early movers. Four industrial sites are considered, i.e., two cement plants from Heidelberg Materials (Hannover, Germany, and Górażdże, Poland), a waste-to-energy plant from KVA Linth (Niederurnen, Switzerland), and a pulp mill from Stora Enso (Skutskär, Sweden). The pioneering chains include CO₂ capture and conditioning from the flue gases at the industrial site, and transport to the closest suitable port. Further ocean shipment to a permanent storage site in Northern Europe, e.g., the Northern Lights or the Porthos storage site, and the storage itself are not included in the boundaries of the analysis. The industrial sites are considered as early movers: only technological solutions currently available are considered for the design of the chains and the techno-economic framework considers first-of-a-kind (FOAK) cost estimates.

The study demonstrates that the pioneering chains can already achieve a CO₂ avoidance between 65% (Górażdże) and 87% (Skutskär) of their industrial emissions. Under this work's assumptions, only Niederurnen and Skutskär have the potential to deliver CDR. The 90% capture rate assumed for the capture process is the main contributor to residual emissions. In addition, direct and indirect emissions also occur along the CCTS chain. The direct emissions are related to the combustion of fuel (CO₂ transport is the main responsible), while the indirect emissions are mostly due to the carbon footprint of electricity. The amount of those emissions is affected by factors such as the length of the transport route and the CO₂ intensity of the energy inputs.

The estimated cost of CO₂ avoided of the pioneering chains lies between 100 and 300 €/tCO₂. The main driver for this variability is the geographic location, which in turn affects the length and complexity of the transport route and the availability of clean and affordable energy. Scale is another important factor, where larger plants can benefit, to some degree, from economy of scale for certain units (e.g., capture and conditioning) compared to smaller ones. The capture plant is, on average, the largest cost share, while the contribution of transport varies extremely depending on the geographical location.

The rollout of the pioneering CCTS chains is characterized by higher costs than typically observed in the literature, due to the additional costs that arise during the demonstration phase of a technology. Assuming that several additional CCTS chains will develop in the future, the maturation of CCTS technologies and infrastructure is expected to result in significant cost reduction (transition from FOAK to NOAK showed to bear expected cost savings larger than 30% for capture and conditioning). This trend is typically observed in new technologies and has already been observed in the case of CCS in the power sector. Still, the associated economic penalty must not translate into delayed implementation. Therefore, this paper discusses potential options to support the burden of early movers and highlights the critical role of targeted policies, e.g., the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, and subsidies schemes. Furthermore, a predictable framework to value CDR can also become essential for those chains that can deliver CDR.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Viola Becattini: Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Luca Riboldi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Johannes Burger:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Julian Nöhl:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Pauline Oeuvray: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Adriana Reyes-Lúa:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Rahul Anantharaman:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **André Bardow:** Review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Linda Frattini:** Investigation, Review. **Chao Fu:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis. **Marco Mazzotti:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Simon Roussanaly:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Cristina Zotică:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Viola Becattini reports a relationship with Neustark that includes: employment. Marco Mazzotti reports a relationship with Neustark that includes: equity or stocks. Andre Bardow reports a relationship with Exxonmobil that includes: consulting or advisory. Andre Bardow reports a relationship with TotalEnergies that includes: consulting or advisory. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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